

SOIL SCIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION ACROSS EUROPE CURRENT STATE AND RECOMMENDATIONS

SUPPORT EUROPEAN COLLABORATIONS IN SOIL SCIENCE HIGHER EDUCATION

Collaborative efforts in higher education should enable European student and staff exchanges.

FUTURE SOIL EXPERTS NEED NEW SKILLS AND KNOWLEDGE

Support diverse active teaching & learning approaches. Support practical & digital activities in soil courses. Update materials to local conditions.

EXPAND OPPORTUNITIES FOR VOCATIONAL, PROFESSIONAL AND LIFELONG LEARNING

Perform an assessment of vocational, professional and lifelong learning opportunities & enhance opportunities for continuous learning in soil science.

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More active teaching and learning approaches and digitalisation are needed

To solve complex sustainability problems, the demand for soil science and land management expertise will increase.

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Photo: Andreas Falmer, SUU

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply.

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ scientists, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL POLICY BRIEF CURRENT STATE

Few higher education institutions have a dedicated soil science department.

Soils and their management are fundamental to essential ecosystems, societal and climate challenges.

The policy brief sheds light on the current state of soil science in European higher education and recommends ways forward to secure European soil science expertise

TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Strengthening scientific capacities and cooperation across Europe including training young soil scientists.

SOIL MISSION: Improve soil literacy in society

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

Policy brief (2021) - Synthesis report of soil science capacity in Higher Education in Europe

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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